

Individual stomatological care plan as a necessity to protect the health of patients with heart-sourcular pathology

Plan de atención estomatologica individual como necesidad para proteger la salud de pacientes con patología cardio-sourcular

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Abstract

Cardiovascular disease (CVD) is one of the leading causes of mortality worldwide, making it an important factor when planning dental treatment. Patients with CVD require a special approach in dental practice, as their health status can significantly influence the choice of treatment methods, anaesthesia and postoperative care. This article discusses the need to develop an individualised dental treatment plan for these patients in order to minimise risks and preserve their overall health.

The focus is on the relationship between dental disease and the cardiovascular system. For example, chronic oral inflammation, such as periodontitis, can exacerbate the course of cardiovascular disease by increasing the risk of heart attacks and strokes. At the same time, certain dental procedures, such as tooth extraction or implantation, can cause a stress response in the body, which is particularly dangerous for patients with CVD.

The authors of the article emphasise the importance of a multidisciplinary approach, including consultation

with cardiologists, to develop a safe and effective treatment plan. Particular attention is paid to the choice of anaesthesia: the use of drugs with minimal impact on the cardiovascular system is recommended. Prevention of infectious complications, which can be particularly dangerous for patients with CHD, is also discussed.

The article provides recommendations for adapting dental treatment for patients with various forms of cardiovascular pathology, including hypertension, ischaemic heart disease and heart failure. The need for careful history taking, risk assessment and ongoing monitoring of the patient during and after treatment is emphasised.

The emphasis is made on the fact that an individual approach to dental treatment of patients with CVD not only improves their quality of life, but also helps to reduce the risk of complications from the cardiovascular system.

Keywords: cardiovascular diseases, dental treatment, individual plan, periodontitis, anaesthesia, interdisciplinary approach, cardiology, prevention, risks, oral health.

La enfermedad cardiovascular (ECV) es una de las principales causas de mortalidad en todo el mundo, por lo que es un factor importante a la hora de planificar el tratamiento dental. Los pacientes con ECV requieren un trato especial en la práctica odontológica, ya que su estado de salud puede influir significativamente en la elección de los métodos de tratamiento, la anestesia y los cuidados postoperatorios. Este artículo analiza la necesidad de desarrollar un plan de tratamiento dental individualizado para estos pacientes con el fin de minimizar los riesgos y preservar su salud general.

La atención se centra en la relación entre las enfermedades dentales y el sistema cardiovascular. Por ejemplo, la inflamación bucal crónica, como la periodontitis, puede exacerbar el curso de la enfermedad cardiovascular al aumentar el riesgo de ataques cardíacos y accidentes cerebrovasculares. Al mismo tiempo, determinados procedimientos dentales, como la extracción o la implantación de dientes, pueden provocar una respuesta de estrés en el cuerpo, lo que es especialmente peligroso para los pacientes con ECV.

Los autores del artículo enfatizan la importancia de un enfoque multidisciplinario, incluida la consulta con cardiólogos, para desarrollar un plan de tratamiento seguro y eficaz. Se presta especial atención a la elección de la anestesia: se recomienda el uso de fármacos con un impacto mínimo sobre el sistema cardiovascular. También se analiza la prevención de complicaciones infecciosas, que pueden ser particularmente peligrosas para pacientes con enfermedad coronaria.

El artículo proporciona recomendaciones para adaptar el tratamiento dental a pacientes con diversas formas de patología cardiovascular, incluida la hipertensión, la cardiopatía isquémica y la insuficiencia cardíaca. Se enfatiza la necesidad de una cuidadosa anamnesis, evaluación de riesgos y seguimiento continuo del paciente durante y después del tratamiento.

Se hace hincapié en el hecho de que un enfoque individualizado del tratamiento dental de los pacientes con ECV no sólo mejora su calidad de vida, sino que también ayuda a reducir el riesgo de complicaciones del sistema cardiovascular.

Palabras clave: enfermedades cardiovasculares, tratamiento odontológico, plan individual, periodontitis, anestesia, abordaje interdisciplinario, cardiología, prevención, riesgos, salud bucal.

Cardiovascular disease (CVD) remains one of the leading causes of mortality and disability worldwide. Patients with this pathology require special attention during any medical interventions, including dental treatment. The link between oral health and cardiovascular health has long been proven: chronic inflammatory processes such as periodontitis can exacerbate CVDs, increasing the risk of heart attacks, strokes and other complications. At the same time, dental procedures, especially invasive ones, can cause stress response of the organism, which poses an additional threat to patients with cardiovascular disorders¹.

This raises the need to develop an individualised dental treatment plan for patients with CVD. This approach should take into account not only the condition of the oral cavity, but also the peculiarities of cardiovascular pathology, which requires close interaction between dentists and cardiologists. Individualisation of treatment allows minimising risks associated with anaesthesia, surgical interventions and postoperative care, as well as contributing to the improvement of the patient's general health.

In the process of writing this work, we studied modern studies on the relationship between oral diseases and cardiovascular system, analysed publications on the impact of dental procedures on patients with CVD, and reviewed recommendations of international organisations (WHO, American Heart Association) on the treatment of patients with concomitant pathologies.

Dental treatment was considered as part of comprehensive medical care for patients with CVD, and the interaction of different body systems (oral cavity, cardiovascular system, immune system) was studied to understand the risks and possible complications.

Through an interdisciplinary approach, knowledge from dentistry, cardiology, anaesthesiology and other medical disciplines was integrated to form a comprehensive treatment approach.

Cardiovascular disease (CVD) is one of the leading causes of mortality and disability worldwide, which determines it as an important factor to consider when planning dental treatment². Patients with CVD represent a special group that requires an individual approach, as their health status can significantly influence the choice of treatment methods, anaesthesia and postoperative care.

It is widely recognised that oral health is closely related to cardiovascular health. Chronic inflammatory diseases such as periodontitis can contribute to the development of atherosclerosis, increasing the risk of heart attacks, strokes and other complications. In addition, dental procedures, especially invasive ones (e.g., tooth extraction, implants, or surgery), can cause a stress response in the body, which is particularly dangerous for patients with CVD³.

In this regard, dental treatment of patients with cardiovascular diseases requires an individual approach, which takes into account not only the state of the oral cavity, but also the peculiarities of cardiovascular pathology. This includes:

- careful collection of anamnesis and risk assessment;
- development of

an individual treatment plan taking into account the severity of CVD;

- selection of safe anaesthesia methods and drugs that minimally affect the cardiovascular system;
- close cooperation with cardiologists to minimise risks;
- prevention of infectious complications that can aggravate the course of CVD⁴.

Thus, taking into account cardiovascular diseases when planning dental treatment becomes an integral part of modern medical practice. This approach not only increases the safety of dental procedures, but also contributes to the general health of patients, improving their quality of life.

The need to develop an individualised dental treatment plan for patients with cardiovascular disease (CVD) is due to the high risk of complications that can occur during and after dental procedures. In these patients, even standard interventions such as caries treatment, tooth extraction or professional oral hygiene can provoke a deterioration of the cardiovascular system due to the body's increased sensitivity to stress, anaesthesia and possible infectious complications⁵.

An individualised treatment plan can minimise the risks associated with cardiovascular disease (CVD), taking into account the characteristics of each patient (Table 1).

Table 1. Individualised treatment plan for patients with cardiovascular disease (CVD)

Stage	Description
1. Thorough diagnosis and assessment of health status	
Anamnesis analysis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Collect information on cardiovascular diseases (CVD), their course and severity. - Clarifying the list of medications taken (anticoagulants, antiaggregants, hypotensive drugs). - Identification of allergies to drugs or materials.
Consultation with a cardiologist	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Determining the risk of complications (e.g. heart attack, stroke, arrhythmia). - Advice on acceptable dental procedures and the need for antibiotic prophylaxis.
Oral health assessment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Identification of priority problems (caries, periodontal disease, need for dentures). - Determination of the scope and sequence of treatment.
2. Choosing safe treatment options	
Use of safe anaesthetics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The use of anaesthetics with minimal or no adrenaline to avoid an increase in blood pressure and stress on the heart. - Consideration of possible allergic reactions.
Minor invasive procedures	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Preferring techniques that are less traumatic to the tissue (e.g. laser therapy, microinvasive caries treatment). - Reducing the stress load on the patient.
Scheduling intermittent procedures	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Division of long procedures into several stages with breaks to monitor the patient's condition. - Monitoring of blood pressure and pulse during treatment.
3. Prevention of complications	
Antibiotic prophylaxis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Administration of antibiotics before invasive interventions (e.g. tooth extraction, periodontal treatment) to prevent infective endocarditis (as indicated).
Stress level control	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Use of sedation (e.g. nitrous oxide) to reduce patient anxiety. - Creating a comfortable environment in the office.
Oral hygiene training	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Advice on proper brushing, use of antiseptic rinses and irrigators. - Teaching the patient to independently monitor the condition of the oral cavity.
4. Interdisciplinary approach	
Collaboration with a cardiologist	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Coordination of treatment with cardiologist to take into account the patient's current condition. - Discuss the need for temporary withdrawal or dosage adjustment of anticoagulants prior to surgical interventions.
Medication records	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Analysis of dental drug interactions with medications the patient is taking. - Correction of the treatment plan if necessary.
5. Long-term follow-up	
Regular examinations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Conducting routine check-ups to monitor oral health. - Timely detection and treatment of new problems.
Correction of the treatment plan	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Modifying the treatment plan in case of deterioration of the cardiovascular system. - Adapting dental procedures to the patient's current condition.

An individualized dental treatment plan for patients with cardiovascular disease aims to minimise the risks associated with their underlying disease and ensure safety during dental procedures. It includes several key steps, each of which requires careful attention⁶.

A thorough diagnosis and health assessment begins with a medical history, where information is collected about cardiovascular diseases, their course and severity, as well as clarifying the list of medications taken and identifying possible allergies. A consultation with a cardiologist is necessary to determine the risk of complications such as heart attack, stroke or arrhythmia and to advise on acceptable dental procedures. An oral health assessment identifies priority problems such as tooth decay, periodontal disease or the need for dentures and determines the extent and sequence of treatment.

The choice of safe treatment methods includes the use of anaesthetics with minimal or no adrenaline to avoid increased blood pressure and cardiac stress⁷. Minimally invasive procedures are preferred, which cause less tissue trauma and reduce the stress load on the patient. Prolonged procedures are planned with intervals to monitor the patient's condition, including blood pressure and pulse monitoring.

Prevention of complications involves administration of antibiotics before invasive interventions such as tooth extractions or periodontal treatment to prevent infective endocarditis. Controlling stress levels through the use of sedation, such as nitrous oxide, and creating a comfortable office environment. Patient education on oral hygiene, including advice on brushing, antiseptic rinses and irrigators, can help reduce the risk of inflammation.

A multidisciplinary approach involves the dentist collaborating with a cardiologist and other specialists to consider the patient's current condition and coordinate treatment. Particular attention is paid to analyzing the interaction of dental preparations with the medications that the patient is taking, and if necessary, the treatment plan is adjusted⁸.

Long-term follow-up includes regular check-ups to monitor oral health and detect new problems in time. If the cardiovascular condition changes, the treatment plan is adjusted to adapt dental procedures to the patient's current condition.

Thus, an individualised treatment plan for patients with cardiovascular disease requires a comprehensive approach that includes thorough diagnosis, safe treatment methods, prevention of complications, interdisciplinary collaboration and long-term follow-up to minimise risks, ensure patient safety and improve quality of life.

The relationship between dental diseases and the cardiovascular system has been the subject of numerous scientific studies. It has been established that chronic inflammatory processes in the oral cavity, such as peri-

odontitis, play a significant role in the development and progression of cardiovascular disease (CVD). The above phenomenon is explained by several mechanisms:

Periodontitis, characterized by chronic inflammation of the gums and destruction of the tissues supporting the teeth, leads to the release of pro-inflammatory mediators such as C-reactive protein (CRP), interleukins (IL-1, IL-6) and tumour necrosis factor (TNF- α) into the blood. These substances contribute to the development of systemic inflammation, which is a key factor in the pathogenesis of atherosclerosis, the main cause of heart attacks and strokes⁹.

In the case of periodontitis, pathogenic bacteria from the oral cavity (e.g. *Porphyromonas gingivalis*) can enter the bloodstream through damaged gum tissue. These bacteria are able to settle on the walls of blood vessels, causing endothelial inflammation and the formation of atherosclerotic plaques. In addition, bacteria can activate the immune response, which enhances damage to the vascular wall¹⁰.

Chronic inflammation in the oral cavity increases the production of free radicals, which leads to oxidative stress. This condition damages vascular cells and promotes the development of atherosclerosis.

Some studies suggest that the bacteria that cause periodontitis can directly affect the heart muscle, increasing the risk of endocarditis and other heart diseases.

Periodontitis and CVD share common risk factors such as smoking, diabetes, obesity and low levels of physical activity. This increases the relationship between the two diseases.

To minimize the risks for patients with cardiovascular disease, the procedure must be carefully planned. This includes prior consultation with a cardiologist to assess the patient's condition, adjustment of anticoagulant or antiaggregant medication, and selection of the optimal time for the procedure based on cardiovascular status.

It is important to use safe anaesthesia, using anaesthetics with minimal or no adrenaline to avoid an increase in blood pressure and heart rate. It is also necessary to provide effective anaesthesia to reduce the stress response¹³.

Thus, dental procedures such as tooth extraction or implantation require special consideration in patients with cardiovascular disease. Adherence to precautions and an individualised treatment plan can minimise risks and ensure patient safety.

The importance of a multidisciplinary approach in the management of patients with cardiovascular disease cannot be overemphasized. Such patients require special attention, as their medical condition can significantly influence the choice of treatment, anaesthesia and postoperative care. The multidisciplinary approach, including consultation with cardiologists, allows us to develop a safe and effective treatment plan that takes into account all aspects of the patient's health.

A cardiologist helps to assess the degree of risk associated with cardiovascular disease and to determine the acceptable limits of stress on the body during dental procedures. This is especially important for patients with severe forms of CVD such as heart failure, coronary heart disease or arrhythmias.

Many patients with SWD are taking medications that may affect dental treatment, such as anticoagulants or antiaggregants. Working together, the dentist and cardiologist can adjust the intake of these medications before the procedure to minimise the risk of bleeding or thrombosis¹⁴.

Based on the cardiologist's recommendations, the dentist can choose the safest treatment options, taking into account the patient's cardiovascular status, which includes choosing minimally invasive procedures, planning long interval interventions, and using specific protocols to reduce stress.

Special attention in the multidisciplinary approach is paid to the choice of anaesthesia¹⁵. For patients with CVD, anaesthetics with minimal cardiovascular effects are recommended. Anaesthetics without or with low levels of adrenaline:

Adrenaline, which is often added to anaesthetics to prolong their effect, can cause an increase in blood pressure and heart rate. For patients with CVDs, this can be dangerous. Therefore, anaesthetics without adrenaline or with minimal concentrations of adrenaline are preferred.

Sedation, such as nitrous oxide, can be used to reduce stress and anxiety in patients with CVD. This minimises stress on the cardiovascular system and makes the procedure more comfortable.

During dental treatment, it is important to continuously monitor the patient's condition, including blood pressure, heart rate, and blood oxygen levels, which helps to detect and prevent possible complications in a timely manner¹⁶.

Thus, a multidisciplinary approach, including consultations with cardiologists, is a prerequisite for successful treatment of patients with cardiovascular diseases. This allows for the development of an individualised treat-

ment plan that takes into account all aspects of the patient's health and ensures maximum safety.

For patients with cardiovascular disease, it is essential to use drugs with minimal cardiovascular effects, especially during dental treatment¹⁷. This situation is due to the fact that many standard drugs, including anaesthetics and other medications, may cause undesirable effects such as increased blood pressure, increased heart rate or arrhythmias, which may aggravate the patient's condition.

Anaesthetics without adrenaline or with minimal concentration of adrenaline are preferred¹⁸. Adrenaline, which is often added to anaesthetics to prolong their effect, can cause vasoconstriction, increased blood pressure and increased heart rate, which is dangerous for patients with hypertension, coronary heart disease or arrhythmias.

Sedation, such as nitrous oxide (laughing gas), can be used to reduce stress and anxiety in patients with CVD. This minimizes stress on the cardiovascular system and makes the procedure more comfortable. Oral sedation (e.g. benzodiazepines) may be used in some cases, but only after consultation with a cardiologist.

Patients at high risk of infective endocarditis (e.g. those with artificial heart valves or heart defects) may be prescribed antibiotics before invasive procedures. The drugs are chosen for their cardiovascular safety and lack of interaction with the patient's other medications.

For postoperative pain relief, drugs with minimal cardiovascular effects such as paracetamol are recommended. Non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) such as ibuprofen should be used with caution as they may increase blood pressure and interact with anticoagulants.

Patients taking anticoagulants (e.g. warfarin) or antiaggregants (e.g. aspirin) require special consideration. The decision to temporarily withdraw or adjust the dose should be made in conjunction with a cardiologist to minimise the risk of bleeding or thrombosis¹⁹.

Thus, the use of drugs with minimal cardiovascular effects is an important aspect of the treatment of patients with CVD. This requires careful selection of medications, consideration of individual patient characteristics and close interaction between dentist and cardiologist. This approach allows to ensure safety and high quality of dental care for patients with cardiovascular diseases.

Prevention of infectious complications in patients with cardiovascular disease (CVD) is the most important aspect of dental treatment²⁰. In these patients, infections are particularly dangerous because they can lead to serious complications, including infective endocarditis, exacerbation of chronic diseases and deterioration of general health.

In patients with heart defects, artificial valves or other structural changes to the cardiovascular system, bacte-

ria that enter the bloodstream during dental procedures can settle on the heart valves, causing infective endocarditis. This life-threatening condition requires long-term treatment and can lead to severe consequences.

Oral infections such as periodontitis or abscesses can cause systemic inflammation that exacerbates the course of cardiovascular disease, increasing the risk of heart attacks, strokes and other complications. Infectious complications can worsen the condition of patients with heart failure, coronary heart disease or other chronic pathologies. Patients at high risk of infective endocarditis (e.g., those with artificial valves, congenital heart disease, or history of endocarditis) should be prescribed antibiotics before invasive dental procedures. Drugs and dosages are selected according to international guidelines (e.g., American Heart Association). Drugs such as amoxicillin or clindamycin are often used.

Aseptic and antiseptic rules should be strictly observed during dental procedures to minimise the risk of infection. Use of sterile instruments, gloves and masks, and treatment of the oral cavity with antiseptic solutions (e.g. chlorhexidine) before the procedure [21].

Prior to routine dental procedures, it is important to eliminate any foci of chronic infection in the oral cavity, such as dental caries, periodontitis or periapical abscesses. Regular professional oral hygiene helps to reduce the risk of inflammation.

Patients with SWD should be informed about the importance of good oral hygiene to prevent infections. Recommendations include regular brushing, flossing and use of antiseptic rinses.

After invasive procedures, it is important to monitor the patient's condition to detect signs of infection (e.g. fever, chills, deterioration of general condition). If symptoms of infection appear, treatment should be started immediately.

Thus, prevention of infectious complications in patients with cardiovascular disease is an important part of dental treatment. It requires a comprehensive approach including antibiotic prophylaxis, aseptic compliance, treatment of foci of infection and patient education. This approach minimizes risks and ensures safe treatment for patients with SWD.

An individualized approach to dental treatment of patients with cardiovascular disease not only improves their quality of life but also helps to reduce the risk of cardiovascular complications. The development of such treatment plans should become a standard in modern dental practice.

Patients with cardiovascular disease are a special group requiring careful and balanced treatment. Given their state of health, dental treatment must be adapted to their needs and capabilities. This includes careful history taking, risk assessment, selection of safe treatment methods and continuous monitoring of the patient's condition²².

A personalized treatment plan can minimize the stress associated with procedures, reduce the risk of complications and ensure patient comfort. For example, the use of anaesthetics with minimal impact on the cardiovascular system, short and minimally invasive procedures, and the prevention of infectious complications help to preserve not only oral health, but also the patient's overall health.

In addition, this approach builds trust between patients and doctor, which is especially important for people with chronic conditions. Patients feel more secure when they know that their treatment takes into account all aspects of their health.

Developing individualized treatment plans for patients with cardiovascular disease should be an integral part of modern dental practice. This not only improves the quality of care provided, but also contributes to a better prognosis for patients by reducing the risk of exacerbations and complications from the cardiovascular system.

Thus, an individualized approach to the dental treatment of patients with cardiovascular disease is an important step towards safer and more effective medical care. Its introduction into everyday practice will help to improve the quality of life of patients and reduce the burden on the health care system.

Conclusions

Cardiovascular diseases (CVD) represent a major challenge for modern dentistry, as they require a specific approach to patient care. Given the close relationship between oral health and cardiovascular health, dental treatment should be tailored to the needs of these patients to minimise risks and ensure safety.

The development of an individualised treatment plan for patients with CVD is a prerequisite for successful dental intervention. Such an approach takes into account the specific cardiovascular pathology, oral and general health of the patient, thus reducing the risk of complications and improving quality of life.

Close co-operation between dentists and cardiologists and other specialists plays a key role in ensuring the safety of treatment. Consultations with a cardiologist help to assess risks, adjust drug therapy and choose the best treatment methods.

The use of anaesthetics with minimal impact on the cardiovascular system, the control of stress and pain, and the prevention of infectious complications are important

aspects of treatment for patients with CVD. Such measures reduce the burden on the body and prevent undesirable consequences.

Regular oral hygiene, treatment of chronic inflammatory processes (e.g. periodontitis) and patient education can help to reduce the risk of exacerbations of cardiovascular disease. Infection prevention, including antibiotic prophylaxis if necessary, also plays an important role. An individualised approach to the treatment of patients with CVDs should become standard in modern dental practice. This not only improves the quality of care, but also improves the prognosis of patients by reducing the risk of complications and exacerbations.

In general, dental treatment of patients with cardiovascular diseases requires a comprehensive and balanced approach. Taking into account the peculiarities of cardiovascular pathology, the use of safe treatment methods and close cooperation with cardiologists can ensure the high quality of dental care and preserve the health of patients. The introduction of such approaches into everyday practice contributes to improving the quality of life of patients and reducing the burden on the health care system.

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